

THE DIGITAL WORLD CONNECTION AND READING PRACTICES OF COLLEGE STUDENTS

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The Digital World Connection and Reading Practices of College Students

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Abstract

Students' connection to digital world is considered important to influence students reading practices and attitude. Contemporary challenges arise as technology reshapes reading practices. This digital immersion has led to a shift from traditional paper-based reading to electronic formats. Consequently, the practice of reading has transformed, impacting lifestyle and information consumption. Using descriptive causal research design employing quantitative approach, this study investigates how digital world connections influence college students' reading practices, particularly as they transition from printed texts to digital technologies with access to a wealth of information. Using quota sampling technique, a total of 371 college students were selected to join the study by answering the self-made survey questionnaire which consists of two parts, the level of digital world connection and level of reading practices. Data gathered were interpreted by frequency count percentage and standard mean deviation while the relationships of the two variables were analysed using simple linear regression analysis. Results revealed the over-all mean score of 3.83 sums up the level of digital connection of the college students which indicates that the level of digital world connection of students in terms of digital literacy skills, use of digital resources for academics, social media use and online academic collaborations is in high level. On the other hand, the overall mean score of 3.77 indicates that the level of reading practices of college students in terms of reading frequency, diversity of reading resources, reading engagement and motivation, and access and utilization of learning resources is in high level also. Regression equation RP (Reading Practices) = $\beta_0 + \beta_1DWC$ (Digital World connection) + ϵ_1 was tested using simple linear regression analysis, results from the ANOVA shows that the sig-value is .540 which is found to be higher than the .05 level of significance set for this study, which implies that digital world connection cannot influence reading practices of college students. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that academic librarians should implement strategies that would make digital resources effective motivators for students to improve reading practices, habits and attitude.

Keywords: library and information science, digital world connection, reading practices, correlation, Philippines

Introduction

Students' connection to digital world is considered important to influence students reading practices and attitude. Contemporary challenges arise as technology reshapes reading practices. Young people, often self-identified as digital natives, grow up surrounded by smartphones, tablets, and e-readers. This digital immersion has led to a shift from traditional paper-based reading to electronic formats. Consequently, the practice of reading has transformed, impacting lifestyle and information consumption. In this context, this study investigates how digital world connections influence college students' reading practices, particularly as they transition from printed texts to digital technologies with access to a wealth of information.

In the global context, many studies had been conducted that correlate the relationship of digital world connection to reading practices. For instance, in Sweden, Statens (2021) discovered that both children and adults experienced reduced reading time due to screen media, leading to lower examination scores. The digital landscape, with its constant distractions from social media, notifications, and web browsing, impedes deep engagement with reading material. Meanwhile, Vazquez-Cano et al. (2020) stated that Spain identified two activities—playing online games via social networks and uploading self-created content—that negatively impacted reading performance. These results underscore the detrimental effects of prolonged technology use outside of school on young people's reading competence.

In Asia, several studies have explored the relationship between reading habits and digital sources. Yusof's (2021) study at Universiti Teknologi MARA examined student reading behaviors in the context of mobile phones, print books, and computers. Notably, 49% of students preferred reading from their mobile phones, while 44% favored print books and 7% opted for computer-based reading. This shift toward online materials reflects the impact of information technology on reading habits, gradually steering students away from traditional printed books. Moreover, social media's pervasive influence cannot be ignored. Liu et al. (2022) observed that prolonged social media use can become a behavioral addiction, detrimentally affecting reading concentration and in-depth engagement. This phenomenon is particularly evident among Chinese students.

In the Philippines, there is a research gap for the researcher was not able to find a study wherein the two variables are present. In the study conducted by Gagalang (2022), teachers expressed concerns about students' reading competence due to excessive use of social media. Interestingly, despite social media platforms being least utilized for educational purposes, students demonstrated positive reading attitudes. They emphasized the importance of reading and found joy in learning new things. However, their frequent engagement with social media posts appeared to diminish their inclination toward productive reading habits. For instance, they were less likely to set aside time for reading during vacant hours or show enthusiasm for advanced reading or reading with friends.. Abiog

(2022) found that despite concerns related to comprehending online materials and intermittent internet connectivity, these students maintained positive attitudes toward online reading and viewing. This suggests that their digital world connection did not necessarily hinder their overall reading practices.

In the local context, the researcher observed that there is a decline in the printed book circulation statistics in the library where she is working. She consulted one academic librarian in a private higher educational institutions in Davao city if she had the same observation in her library. According to her, there was a shift of reading preference among the students like e-books and online articles which they found convenient to do. With that, the interest to conduct this study was initiated to delve into the current reading practices of the college students if it was affected by their digital connectivity.

Research Questions

The aim of the study was to determine if digital world connection influences the reading practices of college students in selected private higher educational institutions in the province of Davao del Sur. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of digital world connection of college students in terms of:
 - 1.1. digital literacy skills;
 - 1.2. use of digital resources for academics;
 - 1.3. social media use; and
 - 1.4. online academic collaborations?
2. What is the level of reading practices among college students in terms of:
 - 2.1. reading frequency;
 - 2.2. diversity of reading materials;
 - 2.3. reading engagement and motivation level; and
 - 2.4. access and utilization of learning resources?
3. Can the digital world connection influence reading practices of college students?

Literature Review

The Digital World Connection of College Students

As technology advances, digital world connection has become integral to our daily routines, shaping our interactions, communication patterns, and self-perceptions. The convenience of instant messaging and virtual communities has facilitated global connectivity, transcending geographical barriers and fostering relationships. However, the constant exposure to virtual communities has also led to challenges especially among college students.

Digital literacy skills.

In a competitive world, including education, a student must be equipped with digital literacy skills in order to survive. Digital literacy is a person's ability to use information and communication technology effectively to access, evaluate, and process information in various digital forms (Manubey et al., 2022). It involves understanding how to use digital tools and resources effectively and responsibly to achieve a desired outcome. Digital literacy skills include basic computer skills, information literacy, media literacy, and critical thinking skills.

However, many individuals and communities lack access to basic digital technologies, especially in rural areas, which limits their ability to develop digital literacy skills. Inadequate digital infrastructure, limited internet connectivity, power cuts, and outdated technology in schools and colleges also limit the development of digital literacy skills among students and educators. As there is an abundance of online information available today, digital literacy requires efficient navigation of such data. (Libago et al,2024).

Use of digital resources for academics

Digital resources play a vital role in promoting students' learning in higher education. Digital learning resources are used for education in many ways and implemented in different forms.

The emergence of digital resources in the teaching-learning environment has brought global competency in the education sector and it continues to progress so the students will be more digitally literate. In the upcoming years, education trends will ride the tide of growing internet capabilities and network capacity, making it easier to incorporate innovative technology into classrooms (Giuffrida & Hall, 2023).

However, the use of e-resources by the students in higher learning institutions has been a major concern to some academic library and information service centers especially in low-income countries like Tanzania which incur higher costs to procure and maintain their e-resources, yet the cost and optimum use of these resources has remained a great challenge. Students do not engage frequently enough in using the available electronic resources within their institutions despite being aware of their existence. Demographic factors (gender, age, level of education), information literacy competency, and individual experience are among the factors observed to influence the use of e-resources in higher learning institutions (Ruzegza & Msonde, 2021).

Social media use

The prevalence of digital reading and the widespread use of social media among young people demands systematic exploration of the effects of social media addiction on students' reading practice. For many, social media provides an ideal platform of connection and expression; however, prolonged social media use holds the danger of becoming a behavioral addiction that threatens to undermine one's reading practice. Social media use tends to have a more significant impact on leisure reading than on academic reading (Liu, 2022).

The emergence of social networks in the university context has contributed to modify students' behaviour, conditioning their academic performance and learning preference (Gomez-Garcia et al., 2023).

The Reading Practices of College Students

Despite the prevalence of digital materials, reading printed resources remains crucial. Print media offers tactile engagement, reduced eyestrain, and better focuses, while digital formats provide convenience and cost-effectiveness. Balancing both formats can enhance students' reading efficiency (Tantig et al., 2023).

Reading Frequency

Reading frequency can have two different meanings depending on the context; the individual reading context and word frequency text. In the context of this study, it relates to individual reading habit on how often someone reads, typically measured in units like number of reading sessions per day/week/month, number of pages read per day/week/month and total reading time per day/week/month. Magsalin(2023) emphasized that although students read on the average of 1 to 4 hours at a time, at many kinds of locations, and for various purposes and mostly on leisure reading materials, these indicate that they had better reading comprehension but may also find difficulty reading based on the type of material and/or external factors like the environment and purpose and some other factors.

(Wang et al ,2022) research study revealed that reading time is the most important factor affecting reading behavior and reading volume. It is found that the reading time of paper books has a significant positive effect on the professional quality of college students, but has no significant effect on the general ability, career and lifetime planning ability of college students. Many students prefer paper books while studying professional knowledge, because they can take notes on them and they are conducive to systemic learning.

Diversity of reading materials

People read for different reasons and purposes. Some of these include entertainment, relaxation, pleasure, and for knowledge.

In terms of physical format on reading choices, printed books (65%) remain the most popular according to Pew Research Center Survey (2021) while audio books remain its spot and e-books has a gradual growth from 25% to 30%. Despite growth in certain digital formats, it remains the case that relatively few Americans only consume digital books (which include audiobooks and e-books) to the exclusion of print (Faverio, 2022).

Reading engagement and motivation

Different scholars hold different views on the connotation of reading engagement, and so far, there are no unified standards. Pearson et al. (2016) believed that reading engagement is the interaction between students' motivation and strategies. Reading motivation is key to our students' success and their abilities to comprehend content, build knowledge, exercise higher level critical thinking skills, and internalize the skill sets that are necessary to productive careers. Investigation of college students' reading motivation is demanded for the field of the higher education.(Huang & Reynolds,2022). The use of internet technologies has changed students' reading patterns and motivation to read. The definition of reading has also been changed by new technologies (e.g., online learning tools, social media sites) in varied social and academic contexts.

Access and utilization of learning resources

Frank et al. (2021) mentioned that access is at the heart of the purpose and work of libraries. Student success in higher education depends on access to digital resources and services, and today's students rely heavily on the library to facilitate that access. The core of all libraries is the ability to provide equitable access to information for users in physical and electronic formats. If students cannot access electronic content or instructional materials, it limits their academic success (Nagle & Vitez, 2021).

Akmad & Abatayo (2024) research examined the effects of unstable internet connectivity on accessing educational resources and collaborative learning among tertiary students. The study highlighted that students experienced task submission delays due to internet connectivity's erratic nature. They also found accessing online resources to be time-consuming. When the internet connection was strong, students accessed resources more quickly, conducted research more efficiently, and submitted their academic tasks on time. Conversely, poor connectivity led to significant delays and increased stress, negatively impacting their academic performance.

Online academic collaborations

Recent studies have shown that students enjoy and are engaged in collaborative learning when it is done digitally with innovative learning technology (Gopinathan et al., 2022).Online academic collaboration has become increasingly popular in recent years, allowing

researchers and students to connect and work together regardless of location and this leads to a wider range of perspectives, expertise, and data, ultimately strengthening research and learning. Its two main aspects are online academic platforms and academic social networks and collaboration tools. Gaad (2022) stressed out that even though students are participating remotely in the teaching and learning process, digital collaboration ensures that everyone gets the chance to share information and retain it.

Furthermore, it was clear in the study of (Akmad & Abatayo,2024) that poor internet connection reduced students' enthusiasm and ability to participate in online collaborative activities, resulting in communication challenges and affecting the promptness of finishing group projects. Mustakim and Adha (2021) discovered that, despite the teacher's ability to use online learning applications effectively, they still had difficulty fostering collaborative learning due to the presence of students in different locations, making coordination challenging.

Relationship between Digital World Connection and Reading Practices of College Students

Reading has a significant number of benefits and the effects of reading practice have been proven in most developed countries. The revolution of technology plays a significant role of unpredictable changes and pervasive effect that has transformed the society nowadays.(Yusof ,2021). Adding on, Hallgren & Bjork (2023) described today's young people from their identities in a world that is increasingly imbued by digital technologies has greater influence on their reading practices. The definition of reading has also been changed by new technologies (e.g., online learning tools, social media sites) in varied social and academic contexts. (Huang & Reynolds,2022)

Based on the related literature and studies presented, there is a relationship between reading practices and digital world connection among students. The level may vary depending on the level of reading practices and digital connection which might be affected by socio-economic status, location, age, digital literacy status, technological limitations in accessibility and digital divide.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative approach, utilizing a descriptive causal research design. Regression analysis is a statistical method used for investigating the relationships between variables, which includes a number of techniques for modelling and analysing several variables.

Respondents

The researcher identified and selected three (3) private higher educational institutions in the province of Davao del Sur. After getting the total student population in each institution, the sample size was computed using the Slovin's formula.

The respondents of the study were 371 college students in different programs and were currently enrolled in the second semester SY 2023-2024.

The Slovin's Formula was used to calculate the total number of respondents and sample size of respondents in every institution. Slovin's formula is used to calculate an appropriate sample size from a population.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Name of Private HEI</i>	<i>Total Student Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
HEI A	1,235	88
HEI B	780	56
HEI C	3,185	227
Total Population	5,200	371

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents in the three (3) chosen private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Davao del Sur. In determining the respondents, Non-Probability Sampling Technique, specifically Quota Sampling, was carried out during the distribution of survey questionnaires.

Instrument

A self-made questionnaire was developed by the researcher in order to facilitate the gathering of the needed data. It is divided into two main parts. The first part pertains to the level of digital world connection with four (4) statements; the second part pertains to the level of reading practices with four (4) statements.

In order to establish the survey questionnaire's reliability and content validity, it went through the following processes. First, it was submitted to the three (3) subject experts for evaluation and assessment of its contents. Second, after thorough revisions and finalization of the survey instrument, they were distributed to thirty-five (35) respondents that meet the research criteria. Because the intention was just to gather initial perception of respondents for pilot testing, convenience sampling technique was applied. Data gathered were processed and tested using Cronbach Alpha to establish reliability and internal consistency.

The first part of the survey assessed the level of digital world connection of college students. The items were answered by asking the

respondents' honest views using a five (5)-point Likert Scale, which is interpreted as follows:

Table 2. Interpretation of Mean Scores on the Respondents' Level of Digital World Connection

<i>A. Digital Literacy Skills</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This implies an extremely high level of students' application of the digital literacy skills in in terms of using search engines effectively, evaluating the credibility of online sources, creating digital content of various formats, understanding copyright and plagiarism issues, operating various digital devices and proficient in online messaging platforms and basic computer skills.
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This implies a high level of students' application of digital literacy skills in in terms of using search engines effectively, evaluating the credibility of online sources, creating digital content of various formats, understanding copyright and plagiarism issues, operating various digital devices and proficient in online messaging platforms and basic computer skills.
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This implies a neutral level of students' application of digital literacy skills in in terms of using search engines effectively, evaluating the credibility of online sources, creating digital content of various formats, understanding copyright and plagiarism issues, operating various digital devices and proficient in online messaging platforms and basic computer skills.
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	This implies rarely level of students' application of digital literacy skills in in terms of using search engines effectively, evaluating the credibility of online sources, creating digital content of various formats, understanding copyright and plagiarism issues, operating various digital devices and proficient in online messaging platforms and basic computer skills.
1	1.00-1.79	Never	This implies that the students never apply the digital literacy skills in very low level in terms of using search engines effectively, evaluating the credibility of online sources, creating digital content of various formats, understanding copyright and plagiarism issues, operating various digital devices and proficient in online messaging platforms and basic computer skills.
<i>B. Use of Digital Resources for Academics</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This suggests an extremely high level of t students' use digital resources like e-books, e-journals, audio Books, digital research tools, digital learning tools and online educational databases.
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This suggests a high level of t students' use digital resources like e-books, e-journals, audio Books, digital research tools, digital learning tools and online educational databases.
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This suggests a neutral level of students' use digital resources like e-books, e-journals, audio Books, digital research tools, digital learning tools and online educational databases.
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	This suggests low level students' use digital resources like e-books, e-journals, audio Books, digital research tools, digital learning tools and online educational databases.
1	1.00-1.79	Never	This suggests very low level students' use digital resources like e-books, e-journals, audio Books, digital research tools, digital learning tools and online educational databases.
<i>C. Social Media Use</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This indicates an extremely high level of students' use of social media like Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, YouTube and Tiktok .
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This indicates a high level of students' use of social media like Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, YouTube and Tiktok .
3	2.60-3.39	Rarely	This indicates a neutral level of students' use of social media like Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, YouTube and Tiktok .
2	1.80-2.59	Rare	This indicates a low level of students' use of social media like Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, YouTube and Tiktok .
1	1.00-1.79	Never	This indicates a very low level of students' use of social media like Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, YouTube and Tiktok .
<i>D. Online Academic Collaborations</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This implies an extremely high level of students' online collaboration activities like discussion rooms, group projects, collaborative writing, peer review, data sharing, and virtual conferences .
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This implies a high level of students' online collaboration activities like discussion rooms, group projects, collaborative writing, peer review, data sharing, and virtual conferences .
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This implies a neutral level of students' online collaboration activities like discussion rooms, group projects, collaborative writing, peer review, data sharing, and virtual conferences.
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	This implies low level of students' online collaboration activities like discussion rooms, group projects, collaborative writing, peer review, data sharing, and virtual conferences.

1	1.00-1.79	Never	This implies a very low level of students' online collaboration activities like discussion rooms, group projects, collaborative writing, peer review, data sharing, and virtual conferences.
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The second part of the survey assessed the level of reading practices of college students. The items were answered by asking the respondents' honest views using a five (5)-point Likert Scale, which is interpreted as follows:

Table 3. Interpretation of Mean Scores on the Respondents' Level of Reading Practices

<i>A. Reading Frequency</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This indicates an extremely high level of reading printed resources like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes.
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This indicates a high level of reading printed resources like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This indicates a neutral level of reading printed resources like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	This indicates a low level of reading printed resources like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes
1	1.00-1.79	Never	This indicates a very low level of reading printed resources like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes
<i>B. Diversity of Reading Materials</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This implies extremely high level of reading diverse materials like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes.
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This implies a high level of reading diverse materials like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes.
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This implies an average level of reading diverse materials like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes.
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	This implies a low level of reading diverse materials like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes.
1	1.00-1.79	Never	This implies a low level of reading diverse materials like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes.
<i>C. Reading Engagement and Motivation</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This suggests an extremely high level of students' engagement and motivation in reading to prepare class notes and exams, update knowledge, learn new words relax and entertain.
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This suggests a high level of students' engagement and motivation in reading to prepare class notes and exams, update knowledge, learn new words, relax and entertain.
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This suggests an average level of students' engagement and motivation in reading to prepare class notes and exams, update knowledge, learn new words, relax and entertain.
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	This suggests a low level of students' engagement and motivation in reading to prepare class notes and exams, update knowledge, learn new words, relax and entertain.
1	1.00-1.79	Never	This suggests a very low level of students' engagement and motivation to read, prepare class notes and exams, update knowledge, learn new words, relax and entertain.
<i>D. Access and utilization of learning resources</i>			
<i>Rating</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	This implies an extremely high level of access and utilization of books, journals, magazines, online electronic databases, and digital resources.
4	3.40-4.19	Often	This implies a high level of access and utilization of books, journals, magazines, online electronic databases, and digital resources.
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This implies a neutral access and utilization of books, journals, magazines, online electronic databases, and digital resources.
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	This implies a low level of access and utilization of books, journals, magazines, online electronic databases, and digital resources.
1	1.00-1.79	Never	This implies a very low level of access and utilization of books, journals, magazines, online electronic databases, and digital resources.

Procedure

The following processes and procedures were strictly followed by the researcher in the conduct of the study. The researcher secured an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School and an Ethical Clearance from the College Research Ethics Committee of Cor Jesu College Inc. The researcher then submitted letters to the HEI's Presidents to seek an approval to conduct the study in their respective institutions. After the approval of the Presidents, the researcher coordinated with the deans of the college and chairpersons in the different curricular programs and arranged the date and time for the administration of the questionnaires. At the same time, the researcher secured an official list of registered students by programs from the registrar. The data gathered were tallied and interpreted as the basis for analysis and findings using the appropriate statistical tool. After arriving with the findings of the study, such findings were shared back to the respondents for purposes of dissemination and validation.

Data Analysis

In order to interpret and analyse all the gathered data, the following statistical tools were used: the frequency count and percentage, mean, standard deviation and simple linear regression analysis.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the study, adhering to ethical procedures was of paramount importance. One such crucial procedure involved obtaining permission from the respondents prior to distributing survey questionnaires. In line with this principle, the researcher had taken the necessary procedures by sending an informed consent letter to the respondents. The letter stated the objectives of the study, along with the role that the respondents play within the research. Moreover, the voluntary nature of participation was emphasized, underlining that respondents were under no obligation to take part in the survey.

Confidentiality was maintained throughout the research process. The researcher underscored the significance of protecting respondents' confidentiality, as a principle that is integral to ethical research practices. By diligently handling the data gathered from the survey questionnaire, the researcher ensured that the privacy of the respondents was upheld, thereby enhancing the credibility and ethical integrity of the study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Digital World Connection of College Students

The first part of the survey was to know the level of digital world connection of the respondents in areas of their digital literacy skills, use of digital resources, social media use and online academic collaborations.

Table 4. Level of Digital World Connection of College Students

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
Digital literacy skills	3.91	Often
Use of digital resources for academics	3.57	Often
Social Media Use	4.26	Always
Online Academic Collaborations	3.57	Often
Overall Mean	3.83	Often

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Extremely High, 3.40-4.19 Very High, 2.60-3.39 Neutral, 1.80-2.59 Low, 1.00-1.79 Very Low

Examining the results above, among the areas of digital world connection indicators, social media has the highest mean score of 4.26. It indicates that the college students use social media like Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, Youtube and Tiktok in extremely high level. These social media platforms had been used as their online educational learning enhancement tools in their subject report presentations.

In today's digital age, social media has become an integral part of our daily lives much more for the college students in the province of Davao del Sur where they are actively engaged with social networks to stay connected, to be informed and to express themselves. Liu (2023) highlights that social media serves as an ideal platform for connection and self-expression. A growing body of literature demonstrates that social media usage has witnessed a rapid increase in higher education and is almost universal among young people (Zhang et al., 2023).

On the other hand, the use of digital resources for academics and online academic collaborations got the same mean score of 3.57, respectively. It implies that the college students have increasingly embraced digital resources, including e-books, e-journals, audio books, and digital research tools. This high level of digital adoption is closely linked to their active participation in online collaboration activities. Students frequently utilize discussion rooms, engage in group projects, collaborate on writing assignments, conduct peer reviews, share data, and participate in virtual conferences.

The over-all mean score of 3.83 sums up the level of digital connection of the college students which indicates that the level of digital world connection of students in terms of digital literacy skills, use of digital resources for academics, social media use and online academic collaborations is in high level. In the upcoming years, education trends will ride the tide of growing internet capabilities and network capacity, making it easier to incorporate innovative technology into classrooms (Giuffrida & Hall, 2023).

Level of Reading Practices of College Students

The second part of the survey aimed to determine the level of reading practices of the respondents in terms of reading frequency, diversity of reading resources, reading engagement and motivation, and access and utilization of learning resources. . Shown in Table 5 are the mean scores with corresponding ratings and interpretation.

Table 5. *Level of Reading Practices*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
Reading frequency	3.63	Often
Diversity of Reading Resources	3.62	Often
Reading engagement and motivation	4.10	Often
Access and utilization of learning resources	3.73	Often
Overall Mean Score	3.77	Often

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Extremely High, 3.40-4.19 Very High, 2.60-3.39 Neutral, 1.80-2.59 Low, 1.00-1.79 Very Low

Reading engagement and motivation received the highest mean score of 4.10 among the various reading practices. It means that the students are engaged and motivated to read and to prepare class notes and exams, update knowledge, learn new words for entertainment and relaxation/recreation. Beyond academic progress, reading contributes to a positive cultural atmosphere and plays a vital role in education within colleges and universities (Wu Wang et al., 2022).

On the other hand, the mean scores for reading frequency (3.62) and diversity of reading resources (3.63) and accessibility and utilization of learning resources (3.73) imply that the students read diverse printed reading materials like textbooks, reference books, fiction books, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious books, subject modules/class notes which are accessed and utilized in high level. The strong utilization of diverse printed reading materials, including textbooks, reference books, fiction works, periodicals, comics/graphic novels, self-help books, religious texts, and subject modules/class notes, is evident among college students. Their high level of engagement with these resources is closely associated with their accessibility and utilization.

Generally, the overall mean score of 3.77 indicates that the level of reading practices of college students in terms of reading frequency, diversity of reading resources, reading engagement and motivation, and access and utilization of learning resources is in high level. This finding was supported by Voung et al. (2021) stating that extensive reading habits help students foster skills such as critical thinking, valuing, adaptability and creativity. College students will read more if diverse learning resources are readily available and accessible for them.

Influence of Digital World Connection Towards Reading Practices

Table 6 shows that when regression equation RP (Reading Practices) = $\beta_0 + \beta_1DWC$ (Digital World connection) + ϵ_1 was tested using Simple Linear Regression Analysis, results from the ANOVA table show that the sig-value is .540 which is found to be higher than the .05 level of significance set for this study

Table 6. *Influence of Digital World Connection Towards Reading Practices*

	<i>Unstandardized Coefficients</i>		<i>Standardized Coefficients</i>		
	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig</i>
(Constant)	3.891	.198		19.627	.000
Digital World Connection	-.032	.052	-.032	-.613	.540

Sig. = .540; *Adjusted r Square* = -.002; *df* = 369

This implies that overall, the model is considered to be not significant and that the model does not fit the data. In addition, the findings indicate a strong evidence that digital world connection cannot influence reading practices. Thus, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis. This means that with the popularity of internet technology, the result does not give any indication that reading has developed in the direction of digitization and mobilization.

Both variables of this study got the high-level results which resulted to the acceptance of the hypothesis that digital world connection cannot influence reading practices among college students. Printed and digital reading resources will remain to be relevant and will be utilized in the coming generation of learners.

Conclusions

The students' digital world connection is influenced by both online academic collaborations and social media presence, with implications on their academic success and well-being. Despite the rising number of digital reading platforms, the college students still utilize and engage in reading printed reading resources. The expansion of reading practices is inevitable as students explore diverse media and sources, driven by their curiosity for learning and knowledge.

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